

Mercedes Pérez Vidal

THE ART, VISUAL CULTURE AND LITURGY OF DOMINICAN NUNS IN LATE MEDIEVAL AND EARLY MODERN CASTILE¹

Despite the increasing interest in female monasticism in Spain, only a few studies have adopted a gender approach in the analysis of liturgy and religious images, including the circumstances of their commission and production². This has obscured the role of women in the creation and performance of music and liturgy, as well as their contribution to the visual, literary, material and devotional culture in their own spaces (such as nunneries) and in the society in which they lived. Only since the 1990s has nuns' artistic production been addressed seriously by art historians, beginning with pioneer publications such as Jeffrey Hamburger's study of German nuns during the Middle Ages³. Since then, many scholars have devoted studies to

¹ Frequent Abbreviations

AFP, Archivum fratrum Praedicatorum; AGOP, Archivio Generale dell'Ordine dei Predicatori, Roma; AHN, Archivo Histórico Nacional (Madrid); AMM, Archivo del Monasterio de Montserrat; AMSDM, Archivo del Monasterio de Santo Domingo el Real de Madrid; AMSDRS, Archivo Santo Domingo el Real de Segovia; AMSDRT, Archivo del Monasterio de Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo; ASMN, Archivio di Stato di Mantova; BAV, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana; BNE, Biblioteca Nacional de España; BNP, Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal; DH, Dissertationes Historicae; MFAHP, Medieval Feminist Art History Project; MMMP, Monastic Manuscript Microfilm Project; MNA, Museu Nacional do Azulejo, Lisbon; MOPH, Monumenta Ordinis Praedicatorum Historica; RAH, Real Academia de la Historia (Madrid); WRM, Wallraf-Richartz-Museum (Cologne).

¹ Much of this article was written with the support of a Postdoctoral Fellowship at UNAM-CH-CIALC.

² Among the works that reassess the role of women in these fields are F. PEREDA ESPESO, *Mencia de Mendoza, mujer del I Condestable de Castilla: el significado del patronazgo femenino en la Castilla del siglo XV*, in B. ALONSO RUIZ - M.C. DE CARLOS - F. PEREDA (a cargo de), *Patronos y coleccionistas: los condestables de Castilla y el arte (siglos XV-XVIII)*, Valladolid 2005, pp. 9-119; T. MARTIN, *Queen as King. Politics and Architectural Propaganda in Twelfth-Century Spain*, Leiden 2006; and Id., *Reassessing the Roles of Women as "Makers" of Medieval Art and Architecture*, Leiden 2012.

³ Cf. J.F. HAMBURGER, *Nuns as Artists: The Visual Culture of a Medieval Convent*, Berkeley 1997, as well as many other works by the same author. Furthermore, several conferences and exhibitions – especially *Krone und Schleier*, which took place in Bonn and Essen in 2005 – also focused on German nuns, have contributed to providing a renewed vision of nuns and nunneries, overcoming the traditional bias of art historians.

Le immagini relative a questo articolo sono alle pp. 480-483.

Italian nuns, focusing on patronage, visual culture and, of course, on artistic production⁴. When considered in light of these advancements in the study of the German and Italian situations, the scarcity of studies on nun artists, on nuns' patronage, and on the visual culture and liturgy of nuns in Spain is striking. This lacuna is even more noticeable the case of Spain's Dominican nunneries, which have been undervalued by art historians in comparison to the convents of other female religious orders.

The few existing studies – mostly monographs – concerning Dominican nuns' art and architecture in Spain, have adopted the traditional methodologies of art history, and in some cases they rely on the idealized interpretations given by the chronicles and official documents. As a result, the role of these women in the creation and performance of liturgy, music and art has been discounted, the general assumption being that they must have closely followed whatever had been established by the friars who oversaw them. Nevertheless, Dominican nuns had their own identity and personality going back nearly to the origins of the Order. This is especially true in the case of the liturgical performance. Indeed, the female Dominicans' constitutions from 1259 establish a clear distinction between theirs and the friars' procedure for reciting the Divine Office. Nuns were to sing it in a solemn and fully articulated way, whereas the friars were to recite it in an abbreviated form, so as to cause less interruption to their studies⁵.

Finally, although feminist scholarship in art history initially overlooked the Middle Ages, since the 1990s this methodological approach has also been applied to this period. Thanks to the aforementioned Hamburger, as well as to Pamela Sheigorn and Paula Gerson, the concept of agency has been extended in the study of medieval art to include not only the artists but also the viewers and the patrons⁶. I will consider this enlarged meaning of

⁴ Cf. M.R. DUNN, *Nuns as Art Patrons: The Decoration of Santa Marta al Collegio Romano*, in «Art Bulletin», 70 (1988), pp. 451-477; C.A. MONSON, *The Crannied Wall: Women, Religion, and the Arts in Early Modern Europe*, Ann Arbor 1992; G.M. RADKE, *Nuns and Their Art. The Case of San Zaccaria in Renaissance Venice*, in «Renaissance Quarterly», 54 (2001), pp. 430-459; A. ROBERTS, *Dominican Women and Renaissance Art, The Convent of San Domenico of Pisa*, Hampshire 2008; K.A. McIVER (ed.), *Wives, Widows, Mistresses, and Nuns in Early Modern Italy. Making the Invisible Visible through Art and Patronage*, Burlington 2012. Among nun artists, the dominican suor Plautilla Nelli, first studied by Giovanna Pierattini in 1938, was probably the most outstanding figure. G. PIERATTINI, *Suor Plautilla Nelli, pittrice domenicana*, in «Memorie Domenicane», 55 (1938), pp. 49-53, 82-85, 168-171, 221-227, 292-297; J. NELSON (ed.), *Suor Plautilla Nelli (1523-1588). The First Woman Painter of Florence*, Florence 2000; ID. (ed.), *Plautilla Nelli (1524-1588): The Painter-Prioress of Renaissance Florence*, Florence 2008.

⁵ According to Dominican nuns' constitutions: «Hore canonicæ omnes in ecclesia tractim et distincte taliter dicantur». «De officio ecclesie», *Constitutiones Sororum Ordinis Fratrum Praedicatorum* (1259), 1, *Constitutiones et Acta Ordinis Fratrum Praedicatorum*, 110 (cf. Const O-P1259, 339). On the contrary, the friars' constitutions ordered «Hore omnes in ecclesia brevier et succinte taliter dicantur en fratres devotionem amittant: et eorum studium minime impediatur». «De officio ecclesie», *Constitutiones Ordinis Fratrum Praedicatorum* (1256), 1, *Constitutiones et Acta Ordinis Fratrum Praedicatorum*, 35 (cf. Const O-P1256*, 36).

⁶ Feminist scholarship excluded, at least during the 1980s, any Western art prior to the early modern period, because its focus on artistic agency, limited this concept to women artists,

agency in my approach to the Dominican nuns in Castile. Moreover, taking into account the continuity of some liturgical and para-liturgical practices between the Middle Ages and the post-Tridentine Early Modern period, as well as continuities in the way of producing, commissioning, and using works of art, the present study will embrace a wide chronology, with examples even from the seventeenth century.

NUNS' AGENCY IN LITURGY AND MANUSCRIPT PRODUCTION

Due to the insufficient knowledge of Spanish nuns' liturgical practices, the study of art and architecture in relation to liturgy – a comparison that has been effectively explored in other countries⁷ – has made little impact in the historiography of Iberian female monasticism⁸. The study of women's liturgical practices has been hampered by several factors: the lack of a gender perspective in this field, the difficulty of consulting monastic archives, and, above all, the disappearance or scattering of most of the manuscripts that once belonged to Castile's Dominican nunneries. The Ecclesiastical Confiscations of Mendizábal (1835-37) should be blamed for much of this loss; in addition, many medieval manuscripts were likely destroyed or replaced after the invention of the printing press, or in the wake of the Order's reform between the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries (particularly the liturgical reform fostered by the General Chapter of Salamanca in 1551)⁹. Among

of whom we have scarce notice for the Middle Ages. *The Medieval Feminist Art History Project* (MFAHP), founded in 1990, tried to overcome this marginalization of Middle Ages in feminist art history. M. BLEEKE, *Feminist Approaches to Medieval Visual Culture: An Introduction*, in «Medieval Feminist Forum», 44/2 (2008), pp. 49-52.

⁷ See for instance G. MUSCHIOL, *Time and Space: Liturgy and Rite in Female Monasteries of the Middle Ages*, in J.F. HAMBURGER - S. MARTI (eds.), *Crown and Veil: Female Monasticism from the Fifth to the Fifteenth Centuries*, New York 2008, pp. 191-206; C. JÄGGI, *Frauenklöster im Spätmittelalter: Die Kirchen der Klarissen und Dominikanerinnen im 13. und 14. Jahrhundert*, Petersberg 2006.

⁸ Among the few works that offer a functional and liturgical approach to the study of nunneries' art and architecture: R. ALONSO ÁLVAREZ, *La cabecera de las iglesias cistercienses femeninas en la Corona de Castilla, Clausura, Cura Monialium y Representación aristocrática y regia*, in «Hortus Artium Medievalium», 5/2 (2009), pp. 341-353; E. CARRERO SANTAMARÍA, *Observaciones sobre la topografía sacra y cementerial de Santa María la Real de las Huelgas, en Burgos, y su materialización arquitectónica*, in F.J. CAMPOS Y FERNÁNDEZ DE SEVILLA (a cargo de), *La clausura femenina en España. Actas del Simposium*, II, San Lorenzo del Escorial 2004, 695-715; C. SANJUST I LATORRE, *L'obra del Reial Monestir de Santa Maria de Pedralbes desde la seva fundació fins al segle XVI. Un monestir reial per a l'orde de les clarisses a Catalunya*, Barcelona 2008.

⁹ As a result, earlier manuscripts that did not conform with the reformed rite had to be remade. Furthermore, due to the availability of printed books, many manuscripts without musical notation lost their value and were therefore destroyed or abandoned. On the contrary, choral books with musical notation were preserved, and continued to be in use thanks to the difficulty of printing such books. B. FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil (ss. XIV-XV) de Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo*, in «Toletana», 19 (2008), pp. 182. Most of the surviving books from Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo were made after the General Chapter of Salamanca and following the new rite, as indicated in a printed diurnal made between 1558 and 1560. This Chapter established

other things, it led to the replacement of both manuscripts and printed books by new ones. Another factor in the dispersion of manuscripts seems to have been their sale in response to economic necessity, and not only in contemporary times. For instance, in a letter addressed to the Marquess of Mantua in 1468, the nuns of Santa Lucia admitted to having sold a breviary to obtain money for repairing their dormitory¹⁰.

A comprehensive survey in monastic archives and libraries would probably bring more exemplars to light, adding to those found by chance, as it happened with a portable breviary accidentally discovered at the monastery of Santo Domingo in Toledo when renovations were undertaken in the novitiate¹¹. As we will see below, this particular nunnery preserves a rich collection of manuscripts from the late fifteenth through the nineteenth century.

In some cases we know the names of the nuns who commissioned, purchased or donated liturgical books. Now in the National Library of Portugal, four books from the Dominican nunnery of Nossa Senhora do Paraíso in Évora were made between 1530 and 1540 in the workshop of Antonio de Holanda. In the colophon of one of these books, a Gradual, there appears the name of the prioress who commissioned it (and very likely the other three as well): Margarida da Gran¹².

the reform of both the breviary and the lectionary, and ordered a full revision of every liturgical book printed in Spain up until then. A. GONZÁLEZ FUENTE, *La vida litúrgica en la Orden de Predicadores. Estudio en su legislación 1216-1980*, Rome 1981 (MOPH, DH), p. 246; FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* (2008), p. 182.

¹⁰ «Notificharemo coma za molti di passati fecesene merchato como patrone da Goito de certe cari de chalzina, avendo venduto uno breviario costrete per volere reparare ali desgracie de questo mondo del nostro dormitorio el qual ruina e va per tera» (ASMN, *Archivo Gonzaga*, 2410, f. 397, cited in G. RONCAGLIA, *Il convento di S. Lucia in Mantova. Indagini e proposte*, Milano 2010-2011, p. 166).

¹¹ This portable breviary is of extreme importance because it is a *unicum*, that is to say, we do not know of other similar exemplars coming from the Dominican nunneries in Spain. It belongs to the group of unnoted liturgical books and it was intended for the personal use of a nun, and not for recitation in the choir. It contains three different parts, independent in origin, but assembled later in a single volume. AMSDRT, ms. 06/508. FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* (2008), pp. 161-188; ID., *El Breviarium Portátil (ss. XIV-XV) de Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo*, in «Ciencia Tomista», 136 (2009), pp. 363-398; ID., *Bloque primitivo del Breviario 06/508 de Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo*, in «Archivo Dominicano», 30 (2009), pp. 103-144. It was probably hidden due the reform, since breviaries were considered luxury items by many reformers, particularly the manuscript ones. For instance, in a letter written to Giovanni Pico della Mirandola in 1495, Savonarola described breviaries as a threat to the nuns' vow of poverty, advocating either printed breviaries held in common, or no breviaries at all. ROBERTS, *Dominican Women*, p. 26.

¹² «Este livro mandou fazer a muyto magnifica e deuota senhora a senhora Margarida da Grana dona prioressa deste moesteiro de Sanct Maria do Paraizo desta muyto nobre cidade d evora acabou se ho an[n]o de Mille d. xxx.vi [1536] pollo mês d agosto. Laus deo. Medina. i(n)dignus». Additional liturgical books from another nunnery in Lisbon, Nossa Senhora da Anunciada, have also survived. Among them are several graduals commissioned by the prioress Joana Silva and copied ca. 1525 by João Fernandes, an *antiphonarium temporale* (ca. 1528), and an *antiphonarium sanctorale* (ca. 1551), ordered by dona Britiz de Meneses, the second prioress of this nunnery, and copied «per soror Antonia indi[g]na serva das servas de Deus». J.P. ALVARENGA, *A Música também é escrita*,

Indeed, prioresses and foundresses frequently played an outstanding role in the constitution and expansion of monastic book collections, not only through commissions of new books, but with purchases as well. Sometimes they bought books from lay dealers, even books not belonging to the Dominican Liturgy (as did Chiara Gambacorta, prioress of San Domenico in Pisa)¹³. Other times they bought books from Dominican friars¹⁴. Aldonza Manuel, prioress of Santa María de Medina del Campo, bought some books from the prior of San Pablo in Peñafiel in 1419¹⁵. The nuns of Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo first borrowed, and then bought, books from the friars of the nearby convent of San Pablo del Granadal¹⁶. In other cases, foundresses, protectors, or even nuns' relatives donated books to a particular nun or nunnery. Due to the inclusion of some English saints, the central and older part of the aforementioned breviary of Santo Domingo in Toledo is thought to have been donated by Queen Catherine of Lancaster to her relatives María de Castilla and Teresa de Ayala, both prioresses in this nunnery between the late fourteenth and the early fifteenth century¹⁷.

in M.V. SUL MENDES (a cargo de), *Tesouros da Biblioteca Nacional*, Lisbon 1992, pp. 253-284; cfr. M.L. MENDES ANDRÉ COELHO FRAZÃO, *Iluminura Renascentista do Convento de Nossa Senhora do Paraíso de Évora. Livros do coro, 136, 137, 138 e 139*, Lisbon 1998.

¹³ Cf. ROBERTS, *Dominican Women*, p. 26.

¹⁴ Books were sometimes sold through nuns. For instance, in 1477 fra Domenico da Pistoia gave several printed copies of the *Legend of Saint Catherine* to the prioresses of San Vincenzo and Santa Lucia so that they could sell these books for the friars. A. THOMAS, *Dominican Marginalia: The Late Fifteenth-Century Printing Press of San Jacopo di Ripoli*, in S.J. MILNER (ed.), *At the Margins: Minority Groups in Premodern Italy*, Minneapolis 2005, p. 201.

¹⁵ «Fray Juan de Peñafiel, prior del monasterio de San Pablo de Peñafiel de la Orden de Predicadores, vende a Doña Aldonza Manuel, priora del monasterio de Santa María la Real de Medina del Campo, unos libros del oficio que habían sido traídos por fray Ferrand García a petición de Johan Carrillo» (AHN, *Clero regular*, Dominicos, Medina del Campo, Leg. 7562, doc.14, cited in M.L. FERNÁNDEZ BAIZÁN, *El Monasterio de Santa María de las Dueñas «El Real» de la villa de Medina del Campo, también llamado Santa María de los Huertos en la Baja Edad Media*, Madrid 1992, p. 44).

¹⁶ They sold a book of the Gospels and a book of the Epistles to María de Castilla, prioress of Toledo, in 1394 «dos libros de pergamino, letra gruesa e nueva, con tablas de madero aforradas en cuero bermejo viejo, conviene a saber: un evangelistero e un pistolero, los cuales libros las prioras que fueron ante de vos e el dicho convento tovieron enprestados de los priores e frayres que pasaron e de nos, prior e frayres, fasta el día qu'esta carta es fecha. E vendemos uso los bien vendidos e bien aforados según buena conciencia a nuestra voluntad e syn premia ninguna por quatroçientos e trynta maravedis» (AMSDRT, 609, cited in FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* [2008], p. 184).

¹⁷ Cf. FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* (2008), p. 184. This part was written in the early 14th century and includes some French rubrics as well as several English saints. Queen Catherine of Lancaster was a great benefactor of the Dominicans. A Dominican reformer, friar Álvaro de Córdoba, was her confessor, and she founded Santa María de Nieva and San Pedro Mártir in Mayorga de Campos. In 1413 she donated to the Dominican nuns of Toledo her houses adjoining their nunnery. Cfr. C. ANIZ IRIARTE - R. CALLEJO DE PAZ, *Real Monasterio de San Pedro Mártir de Mayorga, fundación de la reina Catalina de Lancaster*, Salamanca 1994; A. ECHEVARRÍA ARSUA-GA, *Catalina de Lancaster, reina regente de Castilla (1372-1418)*, Hondarríbia 2002; S. CABALLERO ESCAMILLA, *Palacios y conventos a finales de la Edad Media: la reina Catalina de Lancaster y Santa María la Real de Nieva*, in «Anales de Historia del Arte», no. extra 1 (2012), pp. 267-283.

In a noteworthy related event, Queen Leonor of Albuquerque wrote a letter to the first of these prioresses, María de Castilla, who was also her cousin, with a request to borrow an Ordinary of the Mass in vernacular for the purpose of making a copy. The copy was most likely intended as a gift for the Dominican nunnery of Santa María in Medina del Campo, to which Leonor had donated her houses adjoining the nunnery in 1418¹⁸. This is the evidence for the copying of manuscripts in order to facilitate their transfer among Castilian nunneries implies a «liturgical migration», a phenomenon that has been mainly analyzed in relation to the enforcement of reform. However, in this case and others like it, we are instead dealing with liturgical migration determined by royal patronage and kinship ties between these noblewomen and particular nunneries¹⁹.

Still in regard to this copied Ordinary of Santo Domingo, it would be revealing to discover who carried out the copying of the manuscript. Perhaps it was a Toletan nun? Unfortunately, both the original and copied Ordinaries were destroyed or lost. However, the aforementioned portable breviary of Toledo received two additions, the newer (and more interesting) of which was made for this very Toledo nunnery, between 1460 and 1470, as proven by the inclusion of local festivities, the presence of the nunnery's anagram, and the use of the feminine declension in the rubrics.

Scholars who have dealt with this manuscript have failed to notice that the copyist did not use always the feminine; rather, he or she alternated between female and male in the rubrics, a mistake typically found in manuscripts copied for or by nuns from texts originally written for friars²⁰. So, who copied this part of the breviary and where? As has happened in other cases, female authorship has been strongly denied, as has been the existence of a *scriptorium* in the Toledo nunnery. Scholars instead have attributed both the copied part, as well as the aforementioned Ordinary requested by

¹⁸ Cf. AMSDRT, Doc. 117. The letter is dated c. 1416-24. FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* (2008), p. 184. Santa María la Real in Medina del Campo had its origin in a Premonstratensian nunnery, which was transformed into a Dominican convent in 1402 with the approval of Benedict XIII. J. LÓPEZ, *Tercera parte de la historia general de Sancto Domingo y de su Orden de Predicadores*, Valladolid 2003, p. 28.

¹⁹ Gisela Muschiol defined this concept in connection with the introduction of the observance in German convents. G. MUSCHIOL, *Migrating Nuns – Migrating Liturgy? The Context of Reform in Female Convents of the Late Middle Ages*, in T. BERGER (ed.), *Liturgy in Migration: Cultural Contexts from the Upper Room to Cyberspace*, Minneapolis 2012, pp. 83-100. Regarding the close relation between female members of the Castilian lineage, their agency in the restoration of the lineage, and the role of Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo and Santo Domingo el Real in Madrid in these politics, see M.E. GONZÁLEZ DE FAUVE - I. LAS HERAS - I.P. DE FORTEZA, *Espacios de poder femenino en la Castilla bajomedieval. El caso del linaje de los Castilla*, in «Cuadernos de historia de España», 82 (2008), pp. 99-122.

²⁰ We find similar mistakes in RAH 75 from San Pedro de Cardeña; it includes the *Diadema monachorum* by Smaragdus, which was probably copied for the Cisterian nunnery of Cañas. G. BAURY, *Une bibliothèque médiévale de moniales cisterciennes en Castille. Cañas et les membra disjecta de son missel*, in «Cîteaux. Commentarii cistercienses», 61/2-4 (2010), p. 155. I wish to thank Dr. Baurý for informing me about the new dating of the codex.

Queen Leonor of Albuquerque, to the nearby convent of San Pedro Mártir. However, although these friars had one of the first printing presses in Spain (1483), we have no evidence of the existence of a *scriptorium* in their convent, and so presumably they commissioned their manuscripts from scribes and illuminators in Toledo or elsewhere in Castile²¹. This seems to have been the case with a group of books illuminated between 1490 and 1510 for the confraternity of the Rosary, founded at San Pedro Mártir by Toledo's silk weavers. All of these books disappeared during the Spanish Civil War, but Lorenzo Candelaria has identified from this group a lavish kyrial and several leaves from graduals preserved in American libraries, constituting rare witnesses to music, art, and liturgy in early Renaissance Toledo²².

Despite the high status of the nuns of Santo Domingo, we cannot compare these lavish manuscripts with the nuns' breviary of much lower quality. This was clearly copied for a nun, but was it also copied by a nun? The lower quality of liturgical books produced by nuns has frequently been treated as a problem by art historians, and so they have tended to disregard these *Nonnenarbeiten*, as Hamburger called them. Although in some cases this unskilled decoration has been linked with gender, the question is more complex²³. Indeed, some liturgical books coming from male convents were also produced by inexperienced hands²⁴. Thus, we must be cautious in making such judgments, considering also whether the quality of miniatures was determined by the economic power of the nunnery or convent, or by the patrons, rather than by the gender. Naturally the well endowed nunneries could afford to commission lavish manuscripts from highly skilled artists, such as the illuminated liturgical books from Poissy²⁵. Moreover, there are examples of high quality manuscripts that were illuminated by nuns, such as the gradual written, notated, and decorated around 1300 by Gisela von Kerssenbrock,

²¹ Cf. A. MUNTADA TORELLAS, *Misal Rico de Cisneros*, Madrid 2001, p. 41.

²² The kyrial is now at Yale's Beinecke Library (ms. 794), and Lorenzo Candelaria has identified independent leaves from graduals in the Pierpont Morgan Library, the Detroit Public Library and the Getty Museum. All of them share the same features: the Five Holy Wounds repeated three times on the opening leaves to represent the complete Rosary prayer, and the depiction of the «Knight of Cologne». L. CANDELARIA, *The Rosary Cantoral. Ritual and Social Design in Chantbook from Early Renaissance Toledo*, Rochester 2008, pp. 75-76.

²³ Winston Allen has recently pointed out the change in the style and iconography in the manuscripts produced in the *scriptoria* of German nunneries from the 14th century onwards, i.e., in the wake of the reform. These adopted a «vernacular», «primitive», or «naïve» style – hence the aforementioned concept of *Nonnenarbeiten* – in contrast with the previous production, which looked very much like the friars' books. A. WINSTON-ALLEN, *Gender and Genre in Manuscript Illustration?*, in «Manuscripta», 53/ 2 (2009), p. 214.

²⁴ Cf. A. IMPROTA, *Dal pulpito al sepolcro. Contributo per l'iconografia di San Pietro Martire da Verona tra XIII e XIV secolo*, in «Porticum. Revista d'estudis medievals», I (2011), pp. 105-119.

²⁵ Cf. J. NAUGHTON, *Books for a Dominican Nun's Choir: Illustrated Liturgical Manuscripts at Saint-Louis de Poissy, c. 1330-1350*, in M. MANION - B. MUIR (eds.), *The Art of the Book. Its Place in Medieval Worship*, Exeter 1998, pp. 67-109. In stark contrast to the confraternity founded by Jakob Sprenger in 1475 in Cologne and open to everyone regardless of social status, the Toletan confraternity was restricted to silk weavers and to persons of wealth and status. CANDELARIA, *The Rosary Cantoral*, 116-117.

a cistercian nun at Marienbrunn in Rulle, as stated in the colophon. Von Kerssenbrock depicted herself twice in the work; in one instance she shows herself leading the nuns of Rulle in singing the Christmas hymn, suggesting the close link between liturgical performance and artistic agency²⁶.

Returning to the Toletan breviary, it is clear that whoever the copyist was, she or he was more concerned with the content of the book than with the illumination²⁷. Indeed, one of the striking features of this part of the breviary is the inclusion of nine lessons taken from Ildefonso of Toledo's *De Virginitate perpetua Sancte Marie* in the matins of the Office of the Virgin for Saturday. These protracted lessons are an unusual feature of this breviary, linked with the celebration of the *Expectatio Partus* in Spain on 18 December, in substitution for the Annunciation, as had been established by the Tenth Council of Toledo in 656²⁸. Moreover, the location of these lessons before the Office of the Dead – the place usually occupied by the procession of the Feast of the Assumption – suggests a link between the lessons and the remembrance of the dead.

The rest of the manuscripts still preserved in this nunnery are for the liturgical celebrations in the choir, and not for personal recitation of the Office. These works for the choir include manuscripts with musical notation created both before and (centuries) after the invention of the printing press. One of these antiphonaries demonstrates a recurrent use of the masculine in the rubrics. Are these merely mistakes or was it made for the Dominican convent of San Pedro Mártir? Assuming the latter, we might question whether the nuns reused the convent's books²⁹. In any case, it may also be noted that many of these liturgical books did not have historiated initials or scenes but only geometrical filigree initials decorated in red and blue ink for the major feast days. This decorative system, also used widely in other countries, can be found in a gradual made around 1360 for the convent of the Dominican friars in Dortmund, and created by Elisabeth von Lünen, a nun of Paradies bei Soest, according to the colophon³⁰. In this case, which

²⁶ Now preserved in the Domschatzkammer and Diözesanmuseum of Osnabrück, it included 52 historiated initials and it is notable for its literary quotations from the liturgy. J. OLIVER, *Singing with Angels. Liturgy, Music and Art in the Gradual of Gisela von Kerssenbrock*, Turnhout 2007.

²⁷ It has been argued that in books made for Dominican nuns, the clarity, the content and the meaning were more important than the book illumination, and decoration was reduced to small illustration and visual narrative sequences were avoided. For instance, even in the case of Poissy, the ornamentation is relatively restrained when compared with that of liturgical books (esp. breviaries) made for noble women or even Clarissan nuns like Blanche of France at Longchamp (BAV, cod. Urb. Lat. 603).

²⁸ The reason for this was the prohibition of the coincidence of any festivity with Lent. Although the Annunciation feast was restored in the 11th century, Spain continued to celebrate the *Expectatio Partus* as well.

²⁹ Cf. AMSDRT, Libro no. 17, Antiphonarium from the late XVth century. A catalogue of these books is in M.J. GALÁN VERA - C. MARTÍNEZ GIL - P. PEÑAS SERRANO, *La música en los conventos dominicos de Toledo (siglos XVI–XVIII)*, in «Anales Toledanos», 41 (2005), pp. 279-293.

³⁰ Dortmund Propsteiarhiv, ms. B6, f. 324v: «Hunc librum scripsit, notavit et cum labore complevit soror Elizabet de luenen ordinis fratrum predicatorum in paradysio fratribus eiusdem

is certainly not a unique example, Dominican nuns broke the prohibition against friars ordering books from women (including nuns), established in 1247 by the General Chapter of Trier³¹. In Spain, examples of the abstract decoration of the initials of the major festivities are found in two antiphonaries in the Library of Montserrat. Janini assumed that these antiphonaries once belonged to a Dominican nunnery in Toro. They were undoubtedly reused, as proven by the addition of some sheets with music, and by the rubrics written in vernacular in the margins with indications addressed to the nuns³².

In Italy and Germany, nuns' contributions to the production of manuscripts and early printed books during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries are quite well documented³³. Nuns commissioned and produced – that is to say, copied and illuminated – manuscripts for their own use, and for sale to other religious communities, in some cases sharing the production with friars or secular illuminators³⁴.

Although there are earlier examples³⁵, Italian women were encouraged in these activities by reformers like Giovanni Dominici and Savonarola, and as a consequence, several nunneries had active *scriptoria*. The names of some of

ordinis in tremonia ob perpetuam sui memoriam» (cited in J. HAMBURGER - S. MARTI - D. MASSEY, *Medieval Hypertext: The Illuminated Manuscript in an Age of Virtual Reproduction*, in K. KRAUSE - B. SCHELLEWALD (hrsg.), *Bild und Text im Mittelalter*, Köln 2011 [Sensus: Studien zur mittelalterlichen Kunst, 2], p. 369).

³¹ «Item. Fratres non faciant sibi scribi psalteria vel alia scripta per moniales, vel alias mulieres» (MOPH 3 [1220-1303], *Constitutiones et Acta Ordinis Fratrum Praedicatorum*, 268 [cfr. MOPH 3, 47]). Also, FUEYO SUÁREZ, *El Breviarium Portátil* (2008), p. 167.

³² Cf. AMM, *Antiphonarium de tempore ms. 759* and *Antiphonarium de Sanctis ms. 758*. Both of them arrived at the Montserrat Library in 1918. A. OLIVAR, *Els manuscrits litúrgics de la Biblioteca de Montserrat*, Montserrat 1969 (Scripta et documenta), pp. 55-56; and MMMP 30,043 and 30,045.

³³ In Italy we know of several female *scriptoria*, many of them in Dominican nunneries: San Domenico in Pisa, San Domenico in Lucca, Santa Brigida del Paradiso, Le Murate, San Jacopo a Ripoli, etc. See R. MIRIELLO, *I manoscritti del monastero del Paradiso a Firenze*, Firenze 2007 (Biblioteche e archivi, 16). The second printing press of Florence was founded in San Jacopo a Ripoli in 1476 by two friars from San Marco. Dominican nuns not only provided a site and were involved in the production of books, but they also worked as compositors. M. CONWAY, *The Diario of the Printing Press of San Jacopo di Ripoli, 1476-1484: Commentary and Transcription*, Florence 1999 (Storia della Tipografia e del Commercio Librario, 4). More recently, M. MORETON, «*Scritto di Bellissima Lettera*»: *Nuns' Book Production in Fifteenth and Sixteenth-Century Italy*, Ph.D. diss., Iowa University 2013. On the production of manuscripts by German nuns, C. SAUER, *Zwischen Kloster und Welt: Illuminierte Handschriften aus dem Dominikanerinnenkonvent St. Katharina in Nuremberg*, in J.F. HAMBURGER - C. JÄGGI - S. MARTI - H. RÖCKELEIN (hrsg.), *Frauen-Kloster-Kunst: Neue Forschungen zur Kulturgeschichte des Mittelalters. Internationales Kolloquium im Zusammenhang mit Krone und Schleier: Kunst aus mittelalterlichen Frauenklöstern*, Mülheim an der Ruhr-Turnhout 2007.

³⁴ So did the late-Trecento nuns of Santa Maria del Fiore a Lapo (Florence): they regularly sold their books to the Dominican friars of Santa Maria Novella, who may have later illuminated them. S.T. STROCCHIA, *Nuns and Nunneries in Renaissance Florence*, Baltimore 2009, p. 114.

³⁵ One of the earliest books of the Dominican liturgy, a pre-Humbertian graduale, comes from the convent of St. Katharinenthal in Diessenhofen. Vat. Lat. 10773. A. DIRKS, *De Tribus libris manu scriptis primaevae liturgiae Dominicanae*, in «AFP», XLIX (1979), pp. 5-37.

these nuns copyists and illuminators are known. Suor Eufrosia Burlamacchi in Lucca was under the influence of Savonarola, as was suor Plautilla Nelli in Florence's Santa Caterina da Siena³⁶. Suor Domenica da Recarco da Verona from San Vincenzo in Mantua copied fra Bartolomeo da Modena's *Vita degli frati Predicatori*; her manuscript (Cas-3) is kept in the archive of San Domenico in Bologna³⁷.

In Germany, too, the reform seems to have fostered the development of *scriptoria* in female nunneries. These gave rise to "famous" nuns artists like Sibylla von Bondorf³⁸ from the Poor Clares of Freiburg and the Dominican Barbara Gewichtmacherin who came from Gebweiler to St. Katherine in Nuremberg, where she founded a long tradition of illumination³⁹. Also, although they have not received comparable attention from scholars, the names of some Dominican nun copyists or illuminators from the Iberian Peninsula are known, such as the aforementioned soror Antonia, who copied some antiphonaries and graduals from Nossa Senhora da Annuciada in Lisbon⁴⁰. The same reformers who encouraged manuscript and artistic production were against books for personal use, as they were considered luxury items⁴¹. As a result, many of them were probably destroyed or hidden, as likely was the case with the aforementioned breviary from Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo.

³⁶ Cf. I. TOZZI, *I codici miniati della Domenicana suor Eufrosia Burlamacchi al tramonto dell'età medievale*, in «Pecia», 14 (2011), pp. 95-105. For earlier evidence of book production in nunneries, esp. at Pontetetto (Lucca), see L. VANDI, *Redressing Images: Conflict in Context at Abbess Humbrina's Scriptorium in Pontetetto (Lucca)*, in MARTIN, *Reassessing the Roles of Women*, pp. 783-822.

³⁷ Cf. I. TAURISANO (a cura di), *Il libro d'oro domenicano, volgarizzamento del secolo XV delle Vitae fratrum O.P. di Fra Gerardo de Frachet O.P.*, VIII, Roma 1925, pp. 549 ff.; J. QUÉTIF - J. ECHARD, *Scriptores ordinis praedicatorum*, I, Paris 1719, pp. 806 ff.; II, Paris 1721, p. 823.

³⁸ The manuscripts illuminated by Sibylla von Bondorf are scattered among Leipzig, Freiburg, Karlsruhe, Munich and London. W. HEILAND-JUSTI, *Sibilla von Bondorf: Malerin von heiligen Frauen und Männern*, Lindenberg, 2010; U. BODEMANN-KORNHASS, *Von Schwestern für Schwestern. Miniaturenzyklen der Klarissin Sibylla von Bondorf und ihre Funktion*, in HAMBURGER - JÄGGI - MARTI - RÖCKELEIN (hrsg.), *Frauen-Kloster-Kunst*, pp. 197-213.

³⁹ Cf. J.L. CARROLL, *Subversive Obedience: Images of Spiritual Reform by and for Fifteenth-Century Nuns*, in MARTIN, *Reassessing the Roles of Women*, pp. 703-737; SAUER, *Zwischen Kloster und Welt*, pp. 113-129; H. BUTZER FELLEISEN, «*Instructiones de Officiis Ordinis, Constitutiones*», *Papal Bull, and «Buch der Ersetzung»: Rules and Regulations for the Dominican Nuns and Supplement with History of the Order, Ricketts 198 (cat. no. 13)*, in «A Catalogue of Selected Illustrated Manuscripts. The Indiana University Bookman», 17 (1988), pp. 68-75. Also worthy of note is a database currently under construction, the *Arbeitsgruppe feistliche Frauengemeinschaften im europäischen Mittelalter*, designed to provide a comprehensive index of manuscripts illuminated in women's scriptoria, but only in Germanic lands: <http://www.agfem-art.com/index.html>.

⁴⁰ In the colophon of the *Antiphonarium temporale* of 1551 it is written, «Este livro he do mosteiro de Nossa Senhora da Anunciada e mandoy escrever a madre dona Britz de Meneses segunda priozeza (...) por Soror Antonia indigna serva do Senhor». See G. PEREIRA, *Colecção dos Livros de Côro dos conventos extinctos de Lisboa*, Lisbon 1904, pp. 13-14. P. CARDOSO, *Os Livros de Coro quinhentistas de Soror Antónia: o Antifonário L.C. 131*, in C. BARREIRA FERNANDES (Coord.), *Luz, cor e ouro: manuscritos iluminados da Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal*, Lisboa 2015.

⁴¹ See note 11 above.

WEAVERS OR SELLERS?

It has been shown that in Italy and Germany, the production of textile works was closely linked with the introduction of the reform⁴². It is clear that we must overcome the reluctance to take nunneries seriously as sites of commercial production, but, in the case of the Iberian Peninsula we must also be cautious, as the historiography in many cases still relies on the official chronicles of the Order, without further documentary support. For instance, although the evidence is far from clear, some scholars insist on the existence of an outstanding «escuela de bordados» in the convent of Jesús in Aveiro, producing embroidery not only for this nunnery but also for the nearby friars' convent and other churches⁴³. Coming from this nunnery we have preserved four frontals of notable quality, made between the sixteenth and seventeenth century. Nevertheless, we only have evidence of the commission of these works by some nuns, and not of their production⁴⁴. Important for these commissions was the documented existence in this convent – as in St. Katherinental in Zürich, Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo, or Santo Domingo in Madrid – of antagonistic confraternities dedicated to Saint John the Baptist and Saint John the Evangelist, which competed in the commission of works of art for their respective altars⁴⁵.

According to some scholars, the upper story of the cloister of Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo (a.k.a. «El Moral») was used as workroom for the production of embroideries. However, this is based on an anecdote about Sor Francisca Gudiel in the chronicle of Juan López, which, however, did

⁴² Jane Carroll has examined two tapestries produced by Dominican nuns in Germany. Both have small depictions of nuns working at looms in the margins. Carroll suggests that these images are partly self-portraits and partly devotional images, also serving as exemplars of the Dominican reform to impose a *vita activa* that avoided luxury and sloth. J.L. CARROLL, *Women's Devotions: Reform and Piety in Tapestries by Dominican Nuns*, in J.L. CARROLL - A.G. STEWART (eds.), *Saints, Sinners and Sisters: Gender and Northern Art in Medieval and Early Modern Europe*, Aldershot 2003, pp. 182-201.

⁴³ Cf. D.M. GOMES DOS SANTOS, *O Mosteiro de Jesus de Aveiro*, Lisbon 1963-1967.

⁴⁴ According to Luís de Sousa, the seventeenth-century altar frontal in the Chapel of St. John the Baptist was commissioned by soror Maria Jesus, who took vows in 1664: «Havendo herdado avultados haveres mandou que fossem repartidos pelos familiares mais necessitados não querendo mais que o correspondente ao capital da moderada tença com que havia professado e que ela aplicou à decência do culto divino, às alfaías da sacristia e aos ornatos da capela de S. João Baptista» (L. DE SOUSA, *História de S. Domingos*, Lisbon 1767, p. 761, cited in M.J. MOTA, *Urduidas do Passado, Tesouros do Presente*, in «Amusa», 1 [1999], pp. 25-32).

⁴⁵ Cf. M.J. GALÁN VERA, *La devoción de los Santos Juanes en Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo*, in F.J. CAMPOS Y FERNÁNDEZ DE SEVILLA (a cargo de), *El culto a los santos: cofradías, devoción, fiestas y arte*, San Lorenzo de El Escorial 2008, pp. 251-268. The «Krieg» among the nuns devoted to St. John the Baptist and those devoted to the Evangelist in St. Katharinental was related in the life of Clara Anna von Hochenburg, the first prioress of Schönensteinbach in: J. MEYER, *Buch der Reformacio Predigerordens*, hrsg. B.M. REICHERT, II, Leipzig 1908-1909 (Quellen und Forschungen zur Geschichte des Dominikanerordens in Deutschland, 2/3), pp. 61-62, cited in J.F. HAMBURGER, *The Visual and the Visionary, Art and Female Spirituality in Late Medieval Germany*, Cambridge 1998, pp. 440-441.

not mention the workroom or any other place⁴⁶. Conversely, as proven by both architectonic and decorative features, and also by documentary sources, this level of the cloister probably hold a refectory, and it was likely used as processional space, especially for those performed after Compline⁴⁷. There is, in fact, no documentary evidence of textile production in this nunnery. Instead of making textiles, Santo Domingo el Real nuns owned and controlled their sale in the *Alcaicerías* since 1375 when Enrique II granted them a royal privilege⁴⁸. Nevertheless, during the fifteenth century, the nuns, and especially the prioress María Álvarez de Ayala, were involved in a heated altercation with textile sellers of Toledo regarding the management of the *Alcaicerías*⁴⁹. Thus, the role of Toledo's Dominican nuns in the production of silk and other textiles seems to have been quite different from that of Florentine nuns⁵⁰. The latter had a fundamental role in textile production, whereas their Toletan counterparts reaped benefits from their control of the textile trade.

VISUAL CULTURE AND VIRTUAL PILGRIMAGES: AVOIDING ENCLOSURE

Besides covering the altarpieces during the Holy Week, depictions of the episodes of the Passion were also used to guide nuns' virtual pilgrimages inside the cloister. These practices were already described in the fourteenth-century *Vita* of Blessed Henry Suso, a spiritual guide for Dominican

⁴⁶ «Siendo sacristana mayor, estaba señalando a un bordador lo que avia de hazer y para esto saco una mano que dizen las tenía muy buenas. El bordador dijo. Que linda mano, Dios la bendiga, de lo qual la madre doña Francisca de Gudiel se escandalizó tanto que al punto se fue de allí, y se lavó las manos con tinta tantas vezes que le quedaron en ellas unas manchas leonadas, y la duraron toda la vida» (J. LÓPEZ, *Tercera parte de la historia de Santo Domingo y su Orden de Predicadores*, I, Valladolid 2003, pp. 343-344).

⁴⁷ On the decoration of this cloister and the processions after Compline see M. PÉREZ VIDAL, *Devociones, prácticas espirituales y liturgia en torno a la imagen de Cristo Crucificado en los monasterios de Dominicas en la Edad Media*, in F.J. CAMPOS Y FERNÁNDEZ DE SEVILLA, *Los Crucificados, religiosidad, cofradías y arte*, San Lorenzo de El Escorial 2010, pp. 201-205; ID., *La liturgia procesional de Completas en el ámbito de los monasterios femeninos de la Orden de Predicadores en Castilla*, in «Hispania Sacra» (2016) (in press). M. PÉREZ VIDAL, *Compline and its Processions in the ontext of Castilian Dominican nunneries*, in F. Sabaté, *Life and Religion in the Middle Ages*, Cambridge, 2015, pp. 246-277.

⁴⁸ AMSDRT, no. 1104, Ratification by Enrique III of the privilege granted by Enrique II in 1375 at the request of Inés de Ayala, who had sought «hacer alcaycería y tiendas donde se vendiesen los paños de color en Toledo, y unos mesones donde posen los mercaderes que vengan a venderlos. Por hacer merced a esta señora se lo concede». In her will, Inés de Ayala donated the Alcaicería and the privilege the sell of textiles to her daughter, Teresa de Ayala, and, after their deaths, the nunnery inherited the rights over the alcaicerías. AHN, *Clero*, Legajo 7240, Traslado y censo del testamento que otorgó doña Inés de Ayala.

⁴⁹ For instance, on 22 August 1443, the King Juan II wrote to the prioress María Álvarez de Ayala, asking for all documentation regarding the dispute. Cf. F. CAÑAS GÁLVEZ, *Colección Diplomática de Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo. Documentos Reales (1249-1473)*, Madrid 2010.

⁵⁰ Regarding Florentine nuns and textile production, see STROCCHIA, *Nuns and Nunneries*, pp. 116-144.

nuns⁵¹. He related how he performed a kind of *Via Sacra* visiting altars in the cloister, the chapter house and the choir, which symbolized as many places in the Holy Land. This *Via Sacra* was performed both at night after matins, and after the singing of the *Salve Regina* after Compline⁵².

Such reenactments of the Passion, frequently associated with virtual pilgrimages to Jerusalem or Rome, were also fostered by the reform, especially in the «closed nunneries»; i.e those that adopted enclosure, or had it imposed upon them⁵³. Inside the cloister, the nuns recreated urban processions, as well as places they could not reach, and they were even granted by papal concession the same privileges for these virtual pilgrimages as for real pilgrimages⁵⁴. By doing so, they established inside the cloisters a kind of *heterotopia* that subtly reasserted the nuns' power over the nunnery, following attempts by reformers to deprive them of this power⁵⁵.

The pilgrimages were carried out in the cloister and other convent spaces; in some cases, nuns even built new spaces expressly to hold these celebrations, as at Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo. Obviously, images and

⁵¹ The *Vita* was included in the *Exemplar*, written c. 1362 in collaboration with Elisabeth Stigel, prioress of Töss, which included other books like *The little book of Truth*, *The little book of Eternal Wisdom*, eleven letters and an introduction. HAMBURGER, *The Visual and the Visionary*, pp. 198-200.

⁵² Cf. H. SUSO, *The Life of the Blessed Henry Suso by Himself. Translated from the Original German by Thomas Francis Knox*, London 1865, pp. 51-56.

⁵³ We must distinguish in Castile, as did Creytens in Italy, between closed and open nunneries. R. CREYTENS, *La Giurisprudenza della Sacra Congregazione del Concilio nella Questione della Clausura delle Monache (1564- 1576)*, in «*Apollinaris*», 37 (1964), pp. 252-285; ID., *La riforma dei monasteri femminili dopo i Decreti Tridentini*, in *Il Concilio di Trento e la riforma tridentina*, I, Roma 1965, pp. 46-49.

⁵⁴ Innocent VIII in 1487 conceded the Dominican nuns of St. Katharina in Augsburg the same indulgences obtained by pilgrims travelling to the Seven Basilicas of Rome if they recited three *Pater Nosters* and three *Hail Marys* in three different places in the enclosure as appointed by the prioress. In response to this concession was the commission of seven panels with depictions of the Seven Basilicas of Rome as well as some saints: P.F. CUNEO, *The Basilica Cycle of Saint Katherine's Convent: Art and Female Community in Early Renaissance Augsburg*, in «*Women's Art Journal*», 19 (1998), pp. 21-25; M.L. EHRENSCHWENDTNER, *Virtual Pilgrimages? Enclosure and the Practice of Piety at St Katherine's Convent, Augsburg*, in «*Journal of Ecclesiastical History*», 60/1 (2009), pp. 65-68. Likewise, a papal brief of Alexander VII to the Dominican nuns of Segovia gave to those who visited a chapel or altar in the cloister four times a year, praying for the extirpation of heretics and the glory of the Church, the same indulgences conceded to the pilgrims to Rome. AMSDRS, *Breve de Alejandro VII a la priora y monjas del monasterio. Dado en Roma, en Santa María la Mayor, bajo el anillo del Pescador el día 15 de septiembre de 1661. Año séptimo de nuestro pontificado*. Cfr. K.M. RUDY, *Virtual Pilgrimages in the Convent. Imagining Jerusalem in the Late Middle Ages*, Turnhout 2011.

⁵⁵ Following the definition of heterotopia by Foucault: «Il y a également, et ceci probablement dans toute culture, dans toute civilisation, des lieux réels, des lieux effectifs, des lieux qui ont dessinés dans l'institution même de la société, et qui sont des sortes de contre-emplacements, sortes d'utopies effectivement réalisées dans lesquelles les emplacements réels, tous les autres emplacements réels que l'on peut trouver à l'intérieur de la culture sont à la fois représentés, contestés et inversés, des sortes de lieux qui sont hors de tous les lieux, bien que pourtant ils soient effectivement localisables. Ces lieux, parce qu'ils sont absolument autres que tous les emplacements qu'ils reflètent et dont ils parlent, je les appellerai, par opposition aux utopies, les hétérotopies» (M. FOUCAULT, *Des espaces autres*, in «*Architecture, Mouvement, Continuité*», 5 [Oct. 1984], pp. 46-49).

objects were also involved in those ceremonies. Sometimes, a panel painting depicting all the stations served as a guide for religious women, as was probably the case with a small triptych from San Juan Bautista in Quejana with the *Seven Hours of the Passion*⁵⁶, or the *Panorama of Jerusalem*, a panel in the Clarissan nunnery of Madre de Deus in Lisbon that served as guide for the procession the nuns performed every Friday during Lent, carrying an image of Christ with the Cross and singing various antiphons and the *Miserere*⁵⁷.

The nuns of Santo Domingo el Real in Toledo did penance every Friday during Lent in a room located in the upper story of the cloister (fig. 4), singing the *Miserere* in front of an image of Christ – called «Cristo de las Aguas» – or a *Pietà*⁵⁸. They probably also performed a procession enacting the Passion of Christ in the lower story of this cloister, which was decorated with the *Arma Christi* and the Five Holy Wounds. Although we do not have documentary evidence of these performances in the case of Toledo, we have other examples, for instance in the biography of Sor Lucía de San Ambrosio, a Cistercian nun from Córdoba:

Procuraba cada religiosa elegir para sí la más penosa parte del aparato doloroso que estaba dispuesto para este fin en un rincón del claustro. Allí sobran cruces varias, coronas de espinas, sogas nudosas, disciplinas gruesas y otras diversas insignias⁵⁹.

In the case of Toledo, these celebrations seem to have been linked with the reform, or, to be more precise, with Beata de Piedrahita, a reformer of Dominican nunneries whose spirituality was strongly influenced by Savonarola's piety⁶⁰. Not only do the decoration, the penances, and the com-

⁵⁶ It was probably donated by the King of France and depicts the seven themes of the Hours of the Cross: Judas's Kiss, the Flagellation, the Road to Calvary, the Crucifixion, the Deposition of Christ, the Entombment and the Resurrection. Á. FRANCO MATA, *Triptico de la Pasión de Cristo*, in *Canciller Ayala (Catedral Nueva María Inmaculada, Vitoria, 18 April - 26 July 2007)*, Vitoria 2007, pp. 436-439. According to the author, the triptych can be related to the funerary chapel of Pedro López de Ayala, and to the paraliturgical representations of the Passion from Palm Sunday to the Holy Saturday. In my opinion, however, this representation could have been a recreation of the Passion with different stations, i.e., a precedent of the *Via Crucis*.

⁵⁷ Cf. MNA, *Práticas na fogueira*, ff. 226v-227v, cited in A. PAIS - A. CURVELO, *Memórias da Fogueira. O primitivo mosteiro da Madre de Deus*, in A. CURVELO (a cargo de), *Casa Perfeitíssima: 500 anos da Fundação do Mosteiro da Madre de Deus, 1509-2009*, Lisbon 2009, p. 78.

⁵⁸ Cf. A. SIERRA CORELLA, *Santo Domingo el Real de Toledo. Noticias sobre su fundación y suerte*, in «Revista española de arte», IV/ 7 (1935), p. 307.

⁵⁹ F. CERRATO MATEOS, *El Císter de Córdoba. Historia de una clausura*, Córdoba 2005, p. 224.

⁶⁰ Apart from the similarities between the spirituality of the Beata and that of Savonarola, she expressed her sympathy for Lucy of Narnia and the Ferrarese friar in her religious trial of 1510. See L. SASTRE VARAS, *Proceso de la beata de Piedrahita (I)*, in «Archivo Dominicano», 11 (1990), pp. 359-402; ID., *Proceso de la beata de Piedrahita (II)*, in «Archivo Dominicano», 12 (1991), pp. 337-386. The first Spanish translation of Savonarola, la *Devotísima exposición sobre el psalmo de Miserere mei Deus*, was commissioned by Cardinal Cisneros and published in Alcalá de Henares in 1511. This same year, the cardinal also commissioned the first Spanish translation of the *Vida de Santa Catalina de Siena*. V. BELTRÁN DE HEREDIA, *Las corrientes de espiritualidad entre los domi-*

plex processions performed in this wing support its connection with Beata of Piedrahita, but so do the dates of the wing's construction⁶¹. Indeed, it is also striking to note how the dates of Beata's move to Toledo in 1507 in order to introduce her reforms, the subsequent proclamations of the General Chapter of Zamora, and the veto of her reforms by the Master General one year after, accord precisely with the beginning and interruption of the construction of this area of the cloister⁶².

In Castile, apart from the aforementioned examples of Quejana, Toledo and Segovia, we have also evidence of the enactments of the Passion in Santa María in Medina del Campo, and perhaps also in Madrid⁶³. These performances are documented in other Dominican nunneries as well, such as St. Gertrud in Cologne. At this nunnery is an unusual image (fig. 5) depicting two Dominican nuns carrying the cross. In front of the nuns, a resurrected Christ carrying a flag welcomes the nuns with the words «Komt in mynen wyngart» (Come into my vineyard). Above the cross is the motto, «Gehorsam, Reynlickeit, wonllich Armoyt» (Obedience, purity, and domestic poverty), confirming the links among this depiction, the Passion performances, and the reform of this nunnery. Indeed, the painting is dated 1460-70

nicos de Castilla durante la primera mitad del siglo XVI, in *Miscelánea Beltrán de Heredia*, III, Salamanca 1971-1973, p. 528; G. NIEVA OCAMPO, *La creación de la Observancia regular en el convento de San Esteban de Salamanca durante el reinado de los Reyes Católicos*, in «Cuadernos de Historia de España», LXXX (2006), p. 114.

⁶¹ The influence of Savonarolan mysticism was also documented in the Portuguese court of Manuel I through the sister of the king, Leonor; apropos of this is the use of *Arma Christi* in the decoration of the Hieronymite monastery in Lisbon. P. PEREIRA, *Mosteiro dos Jerónimos*, London 2007, pp. 95-113.

⁶² The rebuilding of this cloister began in 1507, but was interrupted in 1508 when only the south wing and first sections of both the east and west wings were complete. AMSDRT, Doc. 360, Cuenta de los maravedís que se gastaron en las casas de los confesores. Año 1507-1508, and Doc. 361, Noticias de las obras en la cruzja nueva del Patio del Moral, 1508. También noticias de la casa de los confesores. In spite of the support of Cisneros and the Catholic monarchs, the Provincial Chapter of Zamora (1508) enacted regulations against the innovations promoted by her group. That same year, Master General Tomas Vío de Cayetano forbade friars from allowing María de Santo Domingo to introduce reforms in their convents. V. BELTRÁN DE HEREDIA, *Historia de la Reforma*, Roma 1939, pp. 251-253.

⁶³ In the case of Medina del Campo, Gaspar de Alarcón (AGOP, Serie XIV, *Liber Q*, second part, f. 1040) records five chapels in the cloister including one dedicated to the Agony in the Garden, one to the Road to Calvary, and the last with a painting known as the *Santo Cristo de la Vestidura*, which probably depicted the disrobing of Christ. In addition there was another chapel dedicated to the Crucifixion, which was initially located in the chapter house and then moved to the choir; the existence of other chapels is possible. Constanza de Castilla, the prioress of Santo Domingo in Madrid, included in her Book of Devotions a long prayer on the Life and Passion of Christ (C.L. WILKINS, *Constanza de Castilla, Book of Devotions-Libro de devociones y oficios*, Exeter 1998, pp. 1-48). Its 44 chapters seem to relate to a similar practice in the nunnery, and indeed the devotion to the Falls of Christ sometimes had a high number of stations. The Poor Clares of Villingen arranged an astonishing number of altars to commemorate both the Passion and the Holy Places in Jerusalem and Rome. Given the magnitude of the nunnery in Madrid, it probably had a large number of altars, chapels or stations.

and the introduction of the observance in St. Gertrud took place, after years of struggle, on 6 November 1466⁶⁴.

From the end of the fifteenth century onwards, and especially in the wake of the Counter-Reformation, the Catholic Church tried to end the interpolation of unrelated or secular elements into the Divine Office⁶⁵. The enforcement of those prohibitions varied substantially from one place to another: in contrast to cathedrals and parish churches where plays and even liturgical drama were forbidden, nunneries seem to have been a genuine “oasis” for religious plays during most of the early modern period. Moreover, nuns not only performed these religious plays, but in some cases they even wrote them. Apart from the outstanding example of Hildegard of Bingen, there were many others during the Middle Ages. In Castile, Constanza de Castilla (1416-65), the prioress of Santo Domingo el Real in Madrid, was granted special privileges that gave her great influence at the court as well as absolute control over her nunnery⁶⁶. Moreover, Pope Nicholas V authorized Constanza to found a new nunnery, and Esteban de Sotelo, the provincial, entrusted her with its liturgical ordination⁶⁷. As noted above, she wrote a

⁶⁴ WRM 0342. J. PRIEUR, *Das Kölner Dominikanerinnenkloster St. Gertrud am Neumark*, Köln 1983, p. 111. The nuns of San Niccolò in Prato probably performed a kind of virtual pilgrimage and enactment of the Passion. The chapter house of this nunnery was decorated in 1509 by Girolamo Ristori with a *Crucifixion* in the center, the *Road to Calvary* on the left, and the *Lamentation* on the right. Since the Virgin was depicted wearing a dominican habit, the nuns of Prato could identify with her suffering. Moreover, in its *Orto del Gosto* is a rare reproduction of the *Scala Santa*, which was likely a station of an enactment of the Passion for virtual pilgrimages. G. MORINI - S. NICCOLI - D. PALAMEDI, *Un edificio da riscoprire: la Scala Santa in San Niccolò*, in «Prato Storia e Arte», 90-91 (1997) 38, p. 117.

⁶⁵ The Council of Aranda in 1473 established that «quod non fiant in ecclesiis representatines inhonestae dum divina peraguntur» (J. SÁNCHEZ HERRERO, *Concilios provinciales y sínodos diocesanos Toledanos de los siglos XIV y XV*, San Cristóbal de La Laguna 1976, p. 295). In 1610, the Consejo Real ordered to the Valladolid's *alcaldes* to ban comedies from monasteries and churches: «En el Consejo se tiene noticia que en esa ciudad se representan muy de hordinario las comedias en los monasterios y yglesias dellos, con notable escándalo, que mas de la indecencia de representarse cosas profanas delante del Santísimo Sacramento se siguen otros ynconvenitnes en ofensa de Dios Nuestro Señor que conviene evitar. Vm hordenará a los alcaldes de esta Audiencia que tengan cuidado con que no se representen comedias en yglesias de los monasterios de esa ciudad, proveyendo lo que pareciere conveniente para escusarlo...» (M.A. VIRGILI BLANQUET, *Ambiente musical del siglo XVIII en Valladolid*, in ATENEO DE VALLADOLID [a cargo de], *Historia de Valladolid*, V, Valladolid 1984, pp. 280-302).

⁶⁶ She was granted further privileges by Martin V, Eugene V and Calixtus III, as well as by Dominican general master Leonard of Florence, and by the provincials fra Luis de Valladolid and fra Esteban de Sotelo (1449-1454). AHN, *Clero*, Libros 7296. Libro de las licencias y gracias que los sumos pontífices y los Maestros Generales de la Orden de Predicadores concedieron a la Serenísima Señora Doña Constanza Nieta del Rey Don Pero y al Monasterio de Santo Domingo el Real de Madrid donde fue priora 38 años, n.d.

⁶⁷ The 1449 papal bull authorizing the foundation of a Dominican nunnery is in AGOP, *Serie XIV, Fondo Libri*, Liber KKK, f. 574r; AMSDRT, doc. 1713. The second from 1451 confirmed the previous one and endowed the foundation with 8000 maravedís: «per alias nostras literas Inter Cetera quanda domun in Civitate Toletan consistentem in Monasterium Monialium dicti ordinis que imbi subregulari observancia imperpetuum famularentur erigendi construendi fundandi et dotandi licencia concessa extitit» (AHN, *Clero*, Pergaminos, 1365/15, issued 18 May 1451; AHN, *Clero*, Libros 7296. Libro de las licencias y gracias, n.d.).

book with several liturgical offices that was used not only for personal devotion, but also for the communal liturgy in the choir⁶⁸. Similar examples are numerous during the early modern period⁶⁹.

In the same way, nuns, and especially prioresses, exerted their agency in artistic production and artistic commissions. The aforementioned Constanza de Castilla commissioned not only the tomb of her grandfather, King Pedro I, in Santo Domingo el Real de Madrid, but also her own tomb, probably located in the middle of the nuns' choir, serving as an *exemplum* and model of devotion for the community – a role later filled by Chiara Gambacorta of Pisa, and, in the sixteenth century, by Maria Carafa⁷⁰. The latter was the sister of Pope Paul IV and the prioress of Santa Maria della Sapienza in Naples, in whose facade she is represented as a builder and patron of the church. Like Constanza, she too combined female agency with a strong reputation for piety, becoming a model for nuns, and also for the city⁷¹.

From the seventeenth century onwards, there are more nun painters and nun sculptors in Spain (such as clarissan nun Sor Estefanía de la Encarnación, or Andrea, Claudia and Juana Teresa de Mena, the daughters of the sculptor Pedro de Mena who all became cistercian nuns in Malaga) but no such examples have yet been found among the Dominicans⁷². Thus, it is clear that research is needed in this area, especially in light of the studies recently carried out on nun musicians. We must seriously question whether Castilian nuns only valued work as a way to avoid the evils of idleness, as some historians have insisted⁷³. Yet we must also be cautious because not every female name associated with an artwork ought to be identified as the artist. Comparisons with other countries would be fruitful, but they should also take into account the importance of royal and noble patronage in Castile's nunneries, as well as the function of these institutions in connection with political and dynastic interests.

⁶⁸ Cf. WILKINS, *Constanza de Castilla, Book of Devotions*.

⁶⁹ Cf. E. WEAVER, *Convent Theatre in Early Modern Italy: Spiritual Fun and Learning for Women*, Cambridge 2002, p. 1; R. RUSSELL (ed.), *Italian Women Writers. A Bio-Bibliographical Sourcebook*, Westport 1994, p. 370; E. ARENAL - E. SCHLAU, *Untold Sisters. Hispanic Nuns in Their Own Works*, Albuquerque 1989.

⁷⁰ Cf. M. NÚÑEZ RODRÍGUEZ, *El sepulcro de Doña Constanza de Castilla. Su valor memorial y su función anagógica*, in «Archivo Español de Arte», 245 (1989), pp. 52-54; ROBERTS, *Dominican Women and Renaissance Art*, pp. 84-91.

⁷¹ The depiction of the *Assumption of the Virgin* in the vault above the nuns' choir, much like a mystical marriage, must have reminded the nuns of their first prioress's visions of seeing and holding the infant Christ. H. HILLS, *Invisible City: the Architecture of Devotion in Seventeenth-Century Neapolitan Convents*, Oxford 2004; A. LOCONTE, *The Convent of Santa Maria della Sapienza: Visual Culture and Women's Religious Experience in Early Modern Naples*, in *Wives, Widows, Mistresses*, pp. 207-234.

⁷² Sor Estefanía de la Encarnación's autobiography includes several references to her activity as a painter. BNE, mss/7559, *La vida de Sor Estefanía de la Encarnación, monja profesada en el Monasterio de religiosas Franciscas de Nuestra Madre Santa Clara, en esta villa de Lerma*.

⁷³ Cf. O. REY CASTELAO, *Las instituciones monásticas femeninas, ¿centros de producción?*, in «Manuscripts», 27 (2009), pp. 59-76.

* * *

Abstract

Taking into account the enlarged concept of agency that includes not only the artists but also the viewers and the patrons, this article offers an approach to the artistic production, liturgical performance and visual culture in the Dominican nunneries in Castile. Its purpose is to overcome the traditional methodologies and the idealized view offered by previous studies on this field in Spain. I will reassess the role played by some women – both nuns and some female patrons, including noblewomen and queens – in the production and commission of liturgical manuscripts, the production and sale of textiles, the development of liturgical and paraliturgical practices, and finally, in the use of sacred spaces and images. Moreover, a comparison with other Dominican nunneries in Europe, will make the commonalities visible, but also emphasize the peculiarities of Spanish nunneries. The dynastic role played by some of these women – foundresses and prioresses – is in many cases the key to understand the female agency not only as a result of piety but also as a means to show and reinforce their power over the nunnery and beyond.